

Towards a framework for analysing playful interventions - Lessons from a pink sandbox full of dice

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Introduction

The role of play has been gaining importance in modern society; the rising commercial successes of game and toy industries in the past decades are strong indications of it. As this has most notably taken place during recent decades, the colloquial meaning of 'play' is still often associated with something trivial and non-important. Play is what one engages in within their leisure time and out of the context of serious, work, or meaningful. In 1970, play theorist Brian Sutton-Smith wrote about the need to stop framing play only as activity of children, as "anything that children did, was regarded as not important, and as play." (Sutton-Smith, 1970).

Even though playfulness is often associated with children, there is a tradition of thought that points out how beneficial fun and play can be for adults. In her review of research into this area, Jacqueline Miller (1996) reported that humor at work can relieve stress, improve interpersonal skills, and foster creativity and rapid learning, among other things. Hunter, Jemielniak & Postula (2010) examined how the roles of play and work were tightly interwoven in knowledge-intensive work such as programming. The play activities were

Abstract In this article, a playful intervention called "There Are No Rules" (TANR) is analyzed on three levels: interactions, play behaviors, and play episodes. In the course of five months, students and staff of University of Tampere engaged with an art installation placed in OASIS, a group work area that also functions as a living lab. The experiment period was recorded on video and photographed by the users and the research team. Combined analysis of the video data and photography data exposed a rich and successful playful intervention, positioning TANR as the centerpiece of a playful office and campus environment. The analysis is further cultivated as a framework for future analysis of similar experiments.

Keywords *Dice, Play, Participatory installation, Design research, Interactive experiment*

important for pacing work activities, building work identity, socialization, and creativity.

In this article, a playful art installation called "There Are No Rules" (TANR) is analyzed as a playful intervention, and a framework for analyzing future playful installations is proposed. We are interested in examining installations on three different levels: on the level of basic interactions that the users of the artefact engage in, on the level of play behaviors, and on the level of distinct play episodes that emerge from the interventions. These three levels of the framework provide points of view for analyzing and comparing affordances and contexts of playful interventions.

There Are No Rules (TANR) – A playful art installation

There Are No Rules (Heljakka, 2011) is a pink wooden sandbox-type construct, 1.3 meters to a side. The box is filled with approximately 10,000 small six-sided dice that have colorful dots on their sides (Figure 1). Essentially, the installation affords the same type of play as a regular sandbox: free manipulation and arrangement of the contents, albeit with far larger building blocks.

Figure 1. *There Are No Rules (TANR)* and the artist Kati Heljakka in OASIS.

The origins of this sandbox-type installation were rooted in the idea of complete freedom to play in the box as one pleases. After having exhibited this participatory installation at several exhibitions, it soon occurred to the creator that playing itself is a rule-making process (Unt, 2012). Adults interacting with the unexpected research instrument – the bubblegum pink sandbox – used the artwork in ways similar to how one would use a construction toy such as building blocks, whereas children tended to use it as a platform for a rougher type of play, e.g. paralleling play inside a ball pit. For adults, it was typical to build a structure and leave it standing. Children, again, clearly expressed more interest in exploring the physical affordances of the dice – and their own bodies (Heljakka, 2014).

OASIS

TANR was set up as a research instrument in OASIS (Figure 2), a social learning space at the University of Tampere. OASIS is an informal group work space on a university campus, and it is open to all students, staff members, and visitors. The central design tenets of OASIS dictate that the space should be open, social, playful, shared, and informal, and that it should allow opportunistic use (Kultima et al., 2014). OASIS also functions as a Living Lab environment, with four cameras recording its usage for research purposes, and it has been used as a test bed for several experiments, including the Mur Mur seats (see Nummenmaa et al., 2015). The camera data is also used in a longitudinal study that focuses on the effects that playful interventions and furniture reconfigurations have on how OASIS is used.

Related work on playful interventions

Tieben et al. (2014a) discuss strategies for playful persuasion in public places. They present ten design cases of playful installations with the design goal of encouraging teenagers in high school to increase participation in physical activities. The authors derive three design values from their experiences of designing and evaluating the installations: elicit and seduce; emergent play; and resonate with values, emotions and activities. These design values can also be seen in operation in TANR. The installation is a “seducing” invitation to play because of the inherent play affordances of the dice and the low threshold of starting an interaction. Emergent play is seen in how interactions with the installation itself produce physical and social play behaviors, often in unexpected ways. Emergent play is also open-ended, where the players create their own rules, meanings, and interpretations, thus allowing for many different play styles and sustained motivation for play (Tieben et al., 2014b). By allowing many different ways of approaching and encountering the installation, TANR is by its very nature a good fit for emergent play. Lastly, the installation should resonate with the values, emotions, and activities of the target group and the target environment. In the OASIS case, TANR was installed in an informal group work space that explicitly promotes the values of being open, social, and playful.

Similarly to the evaluation strategy used in TANR, Tieben et al. (2014b) emphasize the importance of evaluating the playful installations in situ, for prolonged periods of time, and with large groups of

Figure 2. OASIS space.

people. Otherwise it is not possible to understand properly how the installation really suits the environment's day-to-day activities and what kinds of interactions and play behaviors emerge over time. Using extensive video data allowed us to include even brief interactions in our analysis, while photos and tweets allowed the analysis of emerging play behaviors and play episodes, and overall observations supported the analysis phase.

Data and method

The data for this study was collected from two sources: video footage and photographs. In addition, the research team occasionally observed the users using TANR in person. In OASIS, video data is continuously recorded using four cameras which together capture a complete view of the space. Two of the cameras were used in observing user interactions with the installation, while footage from the other two cameras was used for recording contextual data as necessary. Two deep analysis periods of videos, totaling 14 days, were selected for examination and analysis of user interactions with the installation.

The photograph data comprises 102 pictures in total and is taken from two specific sources. During the study period, users of OASIS and research team members shared pictures of interactions with TANR on social media. These pictures were tracked on Twitter and Instagram using the established OASIS hashtag #oasisutafi. The pictures were archived, and information on who shared the picture and the time and platform of sharing was recorded. The textual descriptions posted with the pictures were also

retained. In addition to the pictures shared on social media, the research team also took pictures during the study period when an interesting situation, or the traces of an interesting situation, were identified.

The identity of the users of TANR was not tracked, but the general population of the OASIS space is a combination of university students, staff, and visitors. OASIS attracts a notable number of international students and visitors due to the default language of the space being English. The typical user of OASIS is a 20+ male or female student of information sciences.

In the spirit of Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2006) the experiment data was analyzed iteratively on three different levels: on the level of interactions, play behaviors, and play episodes. The interactions were analyzed by using the video data, whereas play behaviors and play episodes were identified via photographs. The categories of codes were formed iteratively by several researchers. Once they had been identified from the pictures, the play episodes were analyzed further using the video data. In coding the data, the qualitative data tool Atlas.ti was used together with more traditional tools, such as spreadsheets. The details for the analysis of each level is presented in the *Findings* section and further elaborated into a framework in the *Framework for analyzing playful interventions* section.

Findings

This chapter presents the findings from three distinct levels of analysis: **interactions**, play behaviors, and play episodes. Constructed through observing ongoing

user activity, interactions are the fundamental meaningful ways in which users engaged with the installation, and eleven categories of them were identified: adding, removing, building, breaking, modifying, fiddling, examining, throwing, body interaction, scooping, and taking pictures. Using a different temporal and analytical perspective, wider patterns of play and playfulness, called play behaviors, were observed. Eight categories of **play behaviors** were identified and named, including color play, constructing, environment play, physical play, object play, narrative play, transgressive play, and wordplay. Finally, altogether 42 **play episodes**, or periods of playful user activity and behavior, were identified from the data of photographs. Seven of them were further analyzed using the video data and are highlighted in this article: Floor Face, Kenny Escaping, Thin Towers, Peace, Stripes, Photoshoot, and Red and Blue Ghost.

Interactions

Using the video footage from OASIS, user interactions with the installation were observed. Two observation periods were chosen: the first starting when the installation was first set up in order to explore initial user reactions to the installation, and the second period starting two months later when the installation had become an established feature of the space. For the purposes of the analysis presented in this paper, both periods were examined exploratively and not directly compared with each other. A researcher viewed footage from the two observation periods, taking notes and iteratively defining the interaction categories. The analysis was informed by simultaneous exploration of play behaviors and play cases (described later), which led to revisiting and refining some of the categories.

The interactions were recorded within user sessions. A session was defined to start when a user began an interaction and to end when they left the installation and did not return to resume the interaction momentarily. As such, the duration of the observed user sessions ranged from a few seconds to 2 hours, and they could contain multiple types of interactions: for example, a session might begin as examining a previous user's work, continue as modifying it, and conclude with building something new. Based on the data, the interactions were divided into 11 different categories

- adding: *adding items to the dice box*
- removing: *taking items or dice out of the dice box*
- building: *constructing a specific artifact out of the dice by rearranging or placing the dice one by one*
- breaking: *dismantling a previously built artifact completely or partially*
- modifying: *making changes or additions to a previously built artifact*
- fiddling: *activity that is noncommittal in nature and lacks a definite goal or purpose; playing around with the dice; can be secondary to some other simultaneous activity (e.g. done while talking to someone)*
- examining: *curious and/or focused examination of the dice box contents without physically touching them*

- throwing: *picking up dice from the box and throwing or tossing them back in*
- body interaction: *interacting with the dice box using the whole body, for example by standing, sitting, lying, or walking on the dice*
- scooping: *moving large amounts of dice by scooping them or digging to expose the floor under the dice*
- taking pictures: *photographing the installation, its contents, or users interacting with it*

During the first period, 74 user sessions were observed, and during the second period, 24 sessions were observed. These 98 user sessions involved a total of 129 users and 129 interactions:

Table 1. The occurrences of the interactions on the examined data slice.

Interaction	Occurrences
Fiddling	55
Modifying	27
Building	21
Breaking	5
Throwing	4
Examining	4
Adding	3
Removing	3
Body interaction	3
Scooping	2
Taking pictures	2

By analyzing the footage from two video cameras over two observation periods, we were able to track user interactions with the installation and to divide them into 11 distinct categories. Seven of the interaction types stem from the primary affordances of the installation, focusing around manipulating the dice in different ways. Other interactions used external objects or tools, such as toys that were added to the installation or cameras used for taking pictures, or involve either more extensive physical contact with the installation, such as body interaction, or none at all, such as examining the installation. In the end, the analysis portrays fiddling as TANR's factual main interaction.

In order to achieve a broader understanding of the effects of the interactive installation and phenomena surrounding it, user activities and their results were also approached from the perspective of playfulness and using a different data set, leading to an analysis of play behaviors.

Play behaviors

The data consisted of 102 pictures, 66 of which were taken by the research team, while the rest of the pictures were collected from social media. The pictures were analyzed by first identifying whether they portrayed playing – either traces of earlier play or actual ongoing play. The captions of the shared social media pictures were included in the analysis. 76 of the

images included some traces of play behaviors. These pictures were then analyzed in more detail to categorize different play behaviors.

Although our sample was relatively small, the play behaviors were surprisingly versatile in terms of physicality, expression, and using other objects. Based on the photograph and social media data, we were able to identify at least eight categories, including color play, constructing, environment play, physical play, object play, narrative play, transgressive play and wordplay. Although a comprehensive list of play behaviors was identified, it should be noted that this list is most likely not exhaustive, and some behaviors were left unfound.

Color play includes forming pixel art, text, and other formations by using the colors of the dice. Constructing means stacking dice to form structures, such as pyramids and towers. Environment play takes advantage of the surroundings of the box, namely its borders and the floor under the dice. Physical play is found from the pictures that include active playing around and inside the box, such as sitting among the dice and throwing the dice in the air. Object play uses other objects, such as toys, inside or on the sides of the dice box. In narrative play, users had created stories or scenarios, such as a doll with the dice cleared around it, making it seem like the doll had made a snow angel. Transgressive play is only recorded once in a photo that included a die that had a heart drawn on it. Wordplay is written jokes or witty remarks, typically found as a description of the picture shared on social media. This was the only play behavior found in the actual social media shares, not the actual photos, but not exclusively, as one wordplay behavior written with the dice was also identified.

The discovered play behavior categories were linked to play episodes identified from the pictures (see Table 2). Many play episodes continued in several different pictures, and some episodes included several different play behavior types. For instance, dolls set on the side of the box were identified as both object and environment play. Two categories of play behavior were dominant in TANR: color play and constructing. In the following chapter, the play episodes are examined in detail to further understanding of TANR as a playful installation.

Table 2. The occurrences of play behaviors in connection to play episodes.

Play behavior	Episodes connected	Number of codes
Constructing	19	36
Environment play	14	23
Color play	12	39
Object play	12	19
Wordplay	7	10
Physical play	5	19
Narrative play	3	3
Transgressive play	1	1

Play episodes

As the dice-filled sandbox afforded manipulation of the play pieces, we observed a wide variety of creative and playful activities that often extended into synchronous or asynchronous social episodes. These activities left a mark on the box and were also often photographed by the users. Such manifestations of play as different constructions and constellations were identified from the photograph data by tagging the photos collaboratively using Atlas.ti. A total of 42 smaller play episodes were identified, and selected episodes were analyzed in more detail. This analysis used the video data to determine how the episodes evolved, how many players were involved, and the length of the episodes (see Table 3). The following eight play episodes highlighted from the data represent the variety of play emerging from the experiments. The episodes were named as: Floor Face, Kenny Escaping, Thin Towers, Peace, Stripes, Photoshoot, and Red and Blue Ghost (Figure 3).

In the *Floor Face* episode, a group of six people are standing next to the dice box, deep in conversation. One of them sits on the edge of the box, clears out a small circular area to expose the floor beneath the dice, and then moves to the other side of the box and clears out another similar area. Another person then joins in and clears a linear area, creating a semblance of a face in the box. The first person then modifies the ‘mouth’ to show a smile. Both of them add dice to the circular openings to emphasize their eye-like appearance. Several other people make small modifications to the face, add toys to the box, and take pictures.

In the *Kenny Escaping* episode, one person builds a set of stairs reaching to the edge of the box in about 10 minutes, at one point pausing to talk with two people who have approached the dice box and are observing what is being built. The person then leaves OASIS and comes back with a Kenny figurine (from the South Park animated series), places it on the edge of the dice box next to the stairs, and takes more pictures. The person then leaves the stairs and the figurine in place and remains in OASIS.

In the *Thin Towers* episode, one person starts building a construction, and after a little while, two other people join in, one first and the other a minute or so later. They continue for around 20 minutes, constructing various buildings out of the dice. One person takes off their shoes and sits in the box. Two of the people are co-operating (they are working on the same side of the box and are very close to each other), but the third person appears to be working on their own.

In the *Peace* episode, there is no footage of the initial construction and modifications to the artefact from the first 3 days due to technical difficulties. However, its initial stages were observable from social media pictures, and several interesting interactions could be identified from the later video footage. On the third day of the play episode, a group of five people enters OASIS and examines the dice box for a while. One of them starts modifying the artefact, and 3 others join

1. Floor Face
2. Kenny Escaping
3. Thin Towers
4. Peace
5. Stripes
6. Photoshoot
7. Red and Blue Ghost

Figure 3. Selected TANR play episodes. From left to right: Floor Face, Kenny Escaping, Thin Towers, Peace, Stripes, Photoshoot, and Red and Blue Ghost.

in soon. One additional person joins in later. They add hearts and colored dice to the artefact. The activity lasts approximately 10 minutes. Four days later, on Monday, a single person comes into OASIS, examines the artefact in the dice box for a while, changes the textual component of the artefact, and leaves. The activity lasts approximately 10 minutes. Couple of hours later on the same day a single person picks up a few dice from the box, adds them to the artefact, and leaves. The activity lasts for approximately 20 seconds. On Tuesday one person starts to modify the artefact. Two other people join in very briefly. The activity lasts for less than two minutes. Later on the same day, a person starts to wipe the artefact and build something new. Overall, the Peace episode endured for ten days, constantly evolving into something different.

In the *Stripes* episode, three people stand around the dice box and after a while, two of them start arranging the dice. The third person stays in the sidelines for a minute, helping out a little bit, then joins in on the activity. Patterns of colored stripes start to emerge. After finishing rearranging the entire top layer of dice, they take pictures of the result, stay for a little while, and then leave OASIS. The entire endeavor took about 2 hours and 15 minutes.

In the *Photoshoot* episode, two people enter OASIS, and one of them sets up camera equipment near the dice box. The other person sits in the dice box, and they take photos for a while.

In the *Red and Blue Ghost* episode, a single person starts to clear out the artefact in the center of the dice box on Thursday, to create an even and level surface of white dice, and to gather a set of dice with a red side. This phase of the activity continues for about 1 hour. The first person starts to construct a rendering of a Pacman ghost from the red dice previously set aside. The second person pulls out their phones and appears to take pictures. This phase of the activity lasts for about half an hour. On Friday, one person examines the artefact, takes pictures of it, and then rearranges some of the dice to expand the white 'floor' on which

the Pacman ghost is. On Monday, two people come into OASIS and one of them heads straight for the dice box, puts one foot on the white 'floor', and messes up the dice, avoiding destroying the Pacman ghost, while the other observes. On Wednesday, one person starts building another artefact next to the red Pacman ghost. After finishing what turns out to be a blue Pacman ghost right next to the red one, the builder takes a picture of the dice box and leaves OASIS.

The affordances of the dice and the busy social space enabled asynchronous messaging lasting as long as ten days as an evolving play episode. The box invited people to play in different social constellations: some played alone, yet continuing or contributing to someone else's previous work, some came together as a group and started anew, while some were engaging as a more passive bystander or in autotelic play. Altogether, the play episodes were diverse and there were relatively many of them portraying TANR as a rich platform for play.

These three different levels of analysis build an interesting cross-section of a playful artefact as an intervention in a social space. The different affordances of the artefact and the space promote certain kinds of play activities: the dice afford

Table 3. The selected play episodes, their durations and the number of the people involved.

Name of the episode	Duration of the episode	Number of the people involved
Floor Face	10 min.	6
Kenny Escaping	15 min.	3
Thin Towers	25 min.	3
Peace	10 days	5, 1, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1 (several occasions, in order)
Stripes	2 h 15 min.	3
Photoshoot	5 min.	2
Red and Blue Ghost	7 days	2, 1, 2, 1, 2 (several occasions, in order)

building and the dots on the dice color play, the public space hindered transgressive play and created social chains of asynchronous play, and the box frames the area of play, providing people a safe distance for passive engagement as well as different levels for active engagements. The affordance of permanence of the dice also provided invitations for play as the constructions, object play, and various pixel art creations were evidence of the permission of participation.

Framework for analyzing playful interventions

As the TANR experiment was a successful playful intervention engaging the users in a wide variety of playful interactions and forms of play, future studies of similar artefacts would be beneficial. The three layers identified in the study form an interconnected framework for both design and analysis of similar kinds of playful interventions. The basic atomic interactions in the first layer are determined by the immediate affordances of the different components of the intervention. In the case of TANR, the huge number of dice and the physical dimensions and the location of the sandbox give rise to interaction categories of spatial configuration (building, breaking, and modifying), external (adding, removing, and body interaction), fiddling (fiddling, scooping, and throwing), and observation (examining and taking pictures).

The interplay of these basic interactions together with an aim external to the affordances gives rise to the longer term play behaviors identified in the study. In other words, the analysis level of play behavior takes into account what the players try to achieve within the interaction. For example, the play behavior category constructing is simply a sequence of spatial configuration interactions aiming at more vertical constructions while in color play the aim is to use the spatial configuration to create recognizable iconic or symbolic representations.

The emergence of play episodes is dependent not only on the physical characteristics of the intervention and its immediate surroundings but also on the social dynamics of the environment. In this case, OASIS as an informal group work space on a university campus made the play episodes fluid both over time and in player composition. In synchronous play the players involved in the episode join and leave the interaction at the same time, as exemplified in the Photoshoot episode. TANR also supports asynchronous play even for periods of several days as players are not necessary for maintaining the play state, in this case the physical configuration of the dice in the sandbox. In asynchronous play the players can join and leave the episode as they wish, and in many cases there were no active players at all for long periods of time. Because of its size, TANR also support parallel play where even though the players are playing in the same place at the same time, they are not trying to influence each other's behavior, as was exemplified in the Thin Towers episode.

This framework provides a high-level guide for the analysis of the interactions that can happen in playful interventions. The framework, of course, is not exhaustive and further analyses and design of interventions will provide a more elaborate and effective categorization.

Discussion and future work

The TANR experiment proved to be a rich source for material in creating an initial framework for analyzing playful interventions. The decision to take a three-level approach to the analysis, and to have two distinct data sources, with the added data collected through the in-person observations of the researchers, was effective in shining light into various aspects of TANR.

Due to the affordance for color play and the permanence of the dice, TANR could be interpreted as a type of platform for social graffiti. On a number of studies (Stocker, Dutcher, Hargrove & Cook, 1972; Islam, 2010; Trahan, 2011) analyzing graffiti and the culture surrounding them, humor or playfulness have been found out being amongst the top thematic categories. Looking at the way people interacted with TANR, it also has similarities to graffiti. According to Halsey (2006) for the graffiti artist an unpainted wall is just a blank canvas, an invitation to play. In a similar way a box full of colorful dice can be seen as a canvas with an invitation to play. However, the tactile nature of the dice also afforded notable amount of physical fiddling.

A kind of a sub-set for graffiti, toilet writings, or latrinalia, are an interesting case of public, yet at the same time private playful behavior. As the restroom stall offers almost complete anonymity to graffitiists, contents of latrinalia are usually something people would not write publicly. Still at the same time they are used to convey messages to other toilet users, thus creating a temporal bond between the writer and the others. (Young, 2009.) Interestingly, in the experiment of TANR, only one case of transgressive play was recorded. Even though the art installation was named as something without rules, the activity was somewhat conventional possibly due to the all-encompassing public nature of the installation. Further, the play activities extending over several days resembled the temporal bond noted in the latrinalia. Earlier studies of into play as communication have revealed the generally ambiguous character of playful communication (Mäyrä, 2012).

There is a rising interest in public playful interventions. These interventions include interactive art installations, such as Martin Creed's art piece featuring a room half-full of balloons (Now. Here. This., 2014), and publicity stunts, such as Volkswagen's Piano Stairs (Volkswagen, 2009) or Pearlfisher's pool filled with white ball pit balls (Hooton, 2015). They can also be a result of student research work, as in StreetPong, a game to play while waiting the traffic lights to turn green (Hutchings, 2012). A comparison of different playful installations and their factual interactions could improve our understanding of the design of playful interventions. As a future work, we aim to examine an artefact inspired by Pearlfisher's

experiment – a bathing barrel filled with ball pit balls – in the same context as TANR to find out how much of the similarities and differences among these two cases are formed in terms of interaction, play behaviors, and play episodes.

Conclusions

In this article, a playful intervention (TANR) was analyzed on three different levels – interactions, play behaviors, and play episodes. The three-level analysis proved fruitful, as it provided deeper understanding of the characteristics of the intervention. Based on this analysis, a framework was created to work as a high-level guide for the analysis of playful interactions in playful interventions. The framework, although not yet exhaustive, can be used for future analysis of playful interventions and installations in order to compare different artefacts and their modalities and further develop the framework. The future analysis can be compared to the results of the analysis of TANR, which revealed an artifact where the main interaction was noncommittal fiddling, with various color play and constructing play behaviors resulting in a diverse set of social play episodes.

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